

Aztec-Mexica Temple R of Tlatelolco

also known as "Templo R de Tlatelolco"

By Diana Moreiras, The University of British Columbia

Entry tags: Religious Place, Temple, Mexica, Religious Group

This temple was erected by the Mexica (Aztecs) living in Tlatelolco as one of the temples in their ceremonial-ritual complex. The Temple R was dedicated to their wind deity, Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl. This deity was linked to the main Mexica god Tlaloc, in charge of rain and earth's fertility. As such, ceremonies associated with fertility, rain, and the successful maintenance of agricultural cycles were carried out at this temple. In the 1980s, a team of INAH specialists encountered the remains of several individuals during their excavations at this temple. The individuals, including infants, children and adults, had been sacrificed and placed in particular burial contexts: on the ground and inside pots with several artifacts and ecofacts. This sacrificial event has been linked to a one-time ritual ceremony during the massive drought of 1454-1457 CE (also known as the "famine of 1 Rabbit" based on the Mexica calendar; during the reign of Motecuhzoma I).

Date Range: 1337 CE - 1521 CE

Region: Central Mexico

Region tags: Latin America and the Caribbean,
Central America, Mexico

The Temple R was located within the ceremonial complex of the Aztec-Mexica city-state of Mexico-Tlatelolco, sister city of Mexico-Tenochtitlan, which thrived in the Late Postclassic period (1337-1521 CE). The map illustrates the extent of the Tlatelolco ceremonial complex.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The Tlatelolco ceremonial complex (including the Temple R) is situated west of the largest Basin of Mexico lake called "Lago Texcoco". The Basin of Mexico encompassed five lakes in total.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: The temple is circular and on one end there's a big rectangle that comes out of the circle, very much like a platform with a set of stairs at it's end.

↳ One single feature

– Water channel

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Temple R was located within the Tlatelolco ceremonial complex, which included other structures: the Tlatelolco Great Temple, the Calendar Temple, The Palace, Altar V, the Temple of Paintings, the Coatepantli ("wall of snakes"), the Altar Tzompantli (Temple), Altar D1, and Temples I and J.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– I don't know

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: This temple forms part of the larger Tlatelolco ceremonial complex.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: This temple was built to worship and honor the Mexica deity of wind known as Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl.

– Sacrificial

Notes: There is evidence of human sacrifice and human ritual offerings at this temple. Infants, children, and adults were sacrificed but the large majority among the individuals involves subadults (Guilliem Arroyo 1999; Román Berrelleza 1991).

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the building was enlarged a few times during the Late Postclassic period.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Román Berrelleza, J. A. 1991. A Study of Skeletal Materials from Tlatelolco. In *To Change Place: Aztec Ceremonial Landscapes*, edited by D. Carrasco, pp.9-19. University Press of Colorado, Niwot.

– Source 2: Guilliem Arroyo, S. 1999. *Ofrendas a Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl en México-Tlatelolco: Proyecto Tlatelolco 1970-1996*. Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia, Mexico City.

– Source 3: De la Cruz, I., A. González-Oliver, B. M. Kemp, J. A. Román Berrelleza, D. G. Smith, and A. Torre-Blanco. 2008. Sex Identification of Children Sacrificed to the Ancient Aztec Rain Gods in Tlatelolco. *Current Anthropology* 49(3):519-526.

– Source 1: Moreiras Reynaga, D. K. 2019. *The Life Histories of Aztec Sacrifices: A Stable Isotope Study (C, N, and O) of Offerings from Tlatelolco and the Templo Mayor of Tenochtitlan*. Unpublished PhD Dissertation. Department of Anthropology, The University of Western Ontario, London.

– Source 2: Moreiras Reynaga, D. K., J. Millaire, X. Chávez Balderas, J. A. Román Berrelleza, L. López Luján,

and F. J. Longstaffe. Residential patterns of Mexica human sacrifices at Mexico-Tenochtitlan and Mexico-Tlatelolco: Evidence from phosphate oxygen isotopes. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 62:101296.

– Source 3: López Luján, L. 2018. Cuando la gente "se uno-aconejó": la gran sequía de 1454 en la Cuenca de México. *Arqueología Mexicana* 25(149):36-45.

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Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Water feature

Notes: The water feature would be the causeways or canals that were built by the Mexica (Aztec) people living in Tlatelolco and Tenochtitlan to get around these city-states and across the five lake system within the Basin of Mexico.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.mexicolore.co.uk/aztecs/gods/study-the-wind-god>

– Source 1 Description: Mexicolore article on the Aztec (Mexica) Wind God

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.mexicolore.co.uk/aztecs/ask-us/what-about-tlatelolco>

– Source 2 Description: Mexicolore article on Tlatelolco

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: The excavations at the Tlatelolco ceremonial complex started as a salvage excavation project due to imminent city development back in the 1960s. This temple in particular was excavated starting in 1987 as part of the "Proyecto Tlatelolco" (Tlatelolco Project) funded by the University of Boulder (Colorado) and the Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia (INAH) (Guilliem Arroyo 1999).

↳ Years of excavation:

–Year range: 1987-1996

↳ Name of excavation

–Official or descriptive name: Proyecto Tlatelolco

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: While the answer is "yes" it is important to note that the Spaniards built their church on top of the Tlatelolco Great Temple ("Templo Mayor"; see attached image), creating a palimpsest. Also, apartment buildings were built all around the ceremonial complex so the urban fabric of the city is very much part of this overall space. Nonetheless, the remains of the archaeological buildings, including the Temple R, remain visible and are protected by the INAH within this urban setting.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Notes: Given that religion and politics were intricately intertwined, it is possible that the Mexica emperor (tlatoni) and his political advisors and officials could have commissioned this building and the rest of the Tlatelolco ceremonial complex. However, I'm not aware of information that can corroborate this.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Notes: We do not know for sure, but it is possible that some commoners would have done this labor. Other commoners would have focused on agricultural activities and others in craftsmanship.

Groups:

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: The Mexica built this temple to honor the wind god, Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl and to provide offerings and sacrifices to receive favors, particularly in times of droughts.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

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Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1987-1996

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Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The Tlatelolco ceremonial complex (including the Temple R) is situated west of the largest Basin of Mexico lake called "Lago Texcoco". The Basin of Mexico encompassed five lakes in total.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

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Is the place situated in a rural setting:

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Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

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↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: The temple is circular and on one end there's a big rectangle that comes out of the circle, very much like a platform with a set of stairs at it's end.

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Notes: This temple forms part of the larger Tlatelolco ceremonial complex.

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↳ Worship:

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Notes: This temple was built to worship and honor the Mexica deity of wind known as Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl.

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Notes: There is evidence of human sacrifice and human ritual offerings at this temple. Infants, children, and adults were sacrificed but the large majority among the individuals involves subadults (Guilliem Arroyo 1999; Román Berrelleza 1991).

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↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

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↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the building was enlarged a few times during the Late Postclassic period.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

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Notes: Given that religion and politics were intricately intertwined, it is possible that the Mexica emperor (tlatoani) and his political advisors and officials could have commissioned this building and the rest of the Tlatelolco ceremonial complex. However, I'm not aware of information that can corroborate this.

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↳ Groups:

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

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Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

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Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

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Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: The Mexica built this temple to honor the wind god, Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl and to provide offerings and sacrifices to receive favors, particularly in times of droughts.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– I don't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– I don't know

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

–Percentage: 80

Notes: The entire Tlatelolco ceremonial complex is packed with built monuments.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: The temple likely had wood and other organic materials on it's rooftop. However, those materials did not preserve in the archaeological record so these cannot be examined. Guilliem Arroyo (1999) included a possible reconstruction of how the temple would have looked like (see image attached).

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

Notes: See answer above for a reconstruction of the temple that would have included organic materials such as grass and straw.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica were known to use the volcanic stone called tezontle to build their temples.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Notes: The Basin of Mexico was surrounded by volcanic rocks, where the Mexica could have collected their tezontle stone from to make bricks to build their multiple public buildings and temples.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Limestone

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Stone bricks

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

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↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

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Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

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– Other [specify]: Limestone

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Stone bricks

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

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↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

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↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

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A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– I don't know

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

–Yes [specify]: likely "pulque" as Ehécatl is associated with this alcoholic Mexica drink that is made from the maguey plant.

↳ Offerings of food:

–Yes [specify]: There were ceramics recovered from offerings at this temple so it is likely that these contained foods. Pumpkin and chile seeds were recovered from the excavations (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:147).

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– I don't know

Notes: Some animal remains were recovered from this context, however, it is not clear if these were sacrificed. The animals identified include dog or coyote, quail, wild turkey, aquatic bird (probably *Podylimbus podiceps*), frog, and unidentified fish remains (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:148).

↳ Human sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: infants and children encompass a large group of sacrifices (n = 30) to this deity but adults (n = 11; men and women) were also recovered from the temple's offerings (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:172)..

↳ Sacred objects:

– Yes [specify]: ceremonial ceramic vessels and male and female ceramic figurines; musical instruments, wood scepters with snake-like features, animal bone awl/piercing object (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:149-151, 155-165).

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: obsidian knives, domestic ceramics, copper beads and bracelets, shell pendants and beads, baskets, cotton clothing, wood (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:149-155, 166-172).

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: black, red, blue pigments on sculptures, ceramics, figurines, etc., resin (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:151,153-155).

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica priests and elite planned specific ceremonies during their established (20-day month) ritual calendar for their deities (including Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl) and during exceptional events such as times of famine and drought.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica would prepare for rituals and then would engage in specific performances as part of the ritual ceremony (including sacrifice in some instances). Specific clothing, objects, and food items were used for a range of ritual ceremonies, depending on the festivity and deity honored.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica tended to build ceremonial temples and later enlarge them in the same place. This speaks to the fact that they had to maintain the place and enlarge it as they began to have more resources, laborers, and overall power to do these expansions. Building expansions tended to coincide with the ascension of a new Mexica emperor (tlatoani).

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica were known for being extremely hygienic in their every day practices. Slaves chosen for a sacrificial ritual were bathed ahead of time as part of the cleansing and cleaning of these individuals so that the slave status would be washed away, but also they would end up being clean before being offered to the deities.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There are offerings with sacrificed individuals buried within the offerings (see other sections of the entry for more details). However, there was no particular tomb for an individual. They were all placed by the Tlatelolca as ritual offerings.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: The number is not known but we know that everyone from commoner to noble attended these rituals. The population of Tlatelolco would have been smaller than at Tenochtitlan (200,000) so somewhere under this number.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: during multiple monthly festivals throughout the ritual year as well as during one-time ceremonies.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The priests used intoxicants and some times intoxicants were given to sacrificial victims prior to the sacrificial act. I'm unsure if this was the case for particular rituals held at the Temple R, but these were used regularly enough that this could have been the case.

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– I don't know

Notes: See note above on this. Animal remains were recovered but there is no information available to know if these were sacrificed.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– Yes

↳ Adults

– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Male

Notes: Males were identified based on the osteological analysis (Román Berrelleza 1991; Moreiras Reynaga et al. 2021).

↳ Children

– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Male

– Other/InD

Notes: Based on the chromosomal ancient DNA analysis carried out by De la Cruz et al. (2008), most of the subadults (ages 2 to 7) recovered from the Temple R were identified as male.

↳ Foreigners and/or slaves

– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Male

– Other/InD

Notes: Based on the phosphate oxygen isotope analysis carried out by Moreiras Reynaga and colleagues (2021), we know that one adult male was a foreigner to the Basin of Mexico. The rest of the individuals analyzed had a Basin of Mexico oxygen isotope signal. They could have been born in the area or lived in the region for a long period before their sacrifice. It is possible that many of these individuals were purchased at the well-organized Mexica slave markets.

↳ Elites

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While we know that some times noble children were sacrificed at specific ritual ceremonies, it is uncertain if the individuals sacrificed at this temple would have belonged to the elite class. Since many of the children suffered multiple ailments and illnesses that were identified by Román Berrelleza (1991) in his paleopathological analysis, it is more likely that these children came from lower status households and/or slave markets.

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Yes [specify]: The majority were chosen for sacrifice between the ages of 2 and 7 years old and were male. Researchers have proposed that the subadults may have acted as tiny dwarf-like beings called "tlaloque", who were the rain god Tlaloc's little helpers (Román Berrelleza and Chávez Balderas 2006).

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: This temple was built to honor and worship the wind deity, Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl. However, this is one of several high gods as the Mexica honored multiple deities, which represented different aspects of the natural and human worlds.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Mexica deities had anthropomorphic and zoomorphic features. Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl was depicted with a duckbill mask and sometimes fangs since this deity was associated with rain, wind, and the feathered serpent. Other times, Ehécatl was portrayed with spider monkey features. Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl was the guise that powerful deity Quetzalcoatl used to create the world and escape the Underworld.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl was one of the four sky-bearing deities and is associated with the cardinal points.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Notes: While Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl is not chthonic, this deity did spend time in the Underworld as part of the Mexica creation story. The deity helped create the 5th Sun (latest world we live in) by going down to the Underworld and stealing bones of humans from previous worlds to create new humans. The Underworld deity, Mictlantecuhtli did not like that Ehécatl could go into his realm so easily so he told Ehécatl that if he could get music from a conch shell then he could leave the Underworld. Ehécatl had worms bore holes and bees buzz inside the shell so he made a loud sound, which led to his freedom.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Mexica priests carried out specific ceremonial rituals to honor and communicate with this deity, including human sacrifice and offerings at the base of the temple.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: There were specific months in the Mexica ritual calendar when they held ceremonies/festivals for the rain and wind deities prior to the arrival of the rains to bring a successful and fertile agricultural cycle.

Notes: There were a total of 18 festivals/ceremonies throughout their 18 months of 20 days each. These are known as "veintenas" in Spanish. There are multiple Mesoamerican codices that portray these festivals such as the Florentine Codex written by Frair Sahagún. There is a whole field of study in Mesoamerican history dedicated at studying and analyzing these pictographic texts to better understand the structure and details of these festivals.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– I don't know

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

–Elites

–Non-elites

–Religious professionals

Notes: Sometimes feasting was involved after the ritual ceremonies and everyone participated in it and the elite provided the food for everyone.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: In some instances. See note above about the objects that were recovered from the offerings.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Ceramic pottery, clothing, wood, etc. were also recovered from the offerings. See note above about all of the type of objects that were recovered from the offerings.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the material offerings were interred along with the human remains in specific ways and each offering was composed of a series of objects along with the human remains. The human remains were placed either on the ground or inside ceramic pots.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: The entire community attended the ceremonies in Mexica society.

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The Mexica elites and priests were in charge of arranging the ritual ceremonies so they had to attend and host the ceremonies.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Notes: There were sacrificed individuals placed as offerings in this temple but not as co-sacrifices since there's no particular tomb.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

Notes: Not sure but it is likely that cleansing of the place could have been practiced.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica spent resources to make repairs as well as enlarge their temples in the same location.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: There were priests assigned to each temple so they would be the ones in charge of everything related to the maintenance of the place and of organizing everything for the ceremonies as well.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: As ritual offerings. Individuals were either directly buried on the ground or placed inside ceramic pots at the base of the temple.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: during specific ritual ceremonies of the ritual calendar and during one-time ceremonies.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl was considered a part human/divine deity so he likely would fit within this category.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

- ↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - I don't know

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes

- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No

- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: during specific ritual ceremonies worshipping this particular deity.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There are offerings with sacrificed individuals buried within the offerings (see other sections of the entry for more details). However, there was no particular tomb for an individual. They were all placed by the Tlatelolca as ritual offerings.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Notes: There were sacrificed individuals placed as offerings in this temple but not as co-sacrifices since there's no particular tomb.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: As ritual offerings. Individuals were either directly buried on the ground or placed inside ceramic pots at the base of the temple.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: This temple was built to honor and worship the wind deity, Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl. However, this is one of several high gods as the Mexica honored multiple deities, which represented different aspects of the natural and human worlds.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Mexica deities had anthropomorphic and zoomorphic features. Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl was depicted with a duckbill mask and sometimes fangs since this deity was associated with rain, wind, and the feathered serpent. Other times, Ehécatl was portrayed with spider monkey features. Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl was the guise that powerful deity Quetzalcoatl used to create the world and escape the Underworld.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl was one of the four sky-bearing deities and is associated with the cardinal points.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Notes: While Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl is not chthonic, this deity did spend time in the Underworld as part of the Mexica creation story. The deity helped create the 5th Sun (latest world we live in) by going down to the Underworld and stealing bones of humans from previous worlds to

create new humans. The Underworld deity, Mictlantecuhtli did not like that Ehécatl could go into his realm so easily so he told Ehécatl that if he could get music from a conch shell then he could leave the Underworld. Ehécatl had worms bore holes and bees buzz inside the shell so he made a loud sound, which led to his freedom.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Mexica priests carried out specific ceremonial rituals to honor and communicate with this deity, including human sacrifice and offerings at the base of the temple.

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

Are previously human spirits present:
– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– I don't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:
– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:
– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:
– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: during specific ritual ceremonies of the ritual calendar and during one-time ceremonies.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl was considered a part human/divine deity so he likely would fit within this category.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– I don't know

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: during specific ritual ceremonies worshipping this particular deity.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

–Yes [specify]: likely "pulque" as Ehécatl is associated with this alcoholic Mexica drink that is made from the maguey plant.

↳ Offerings of food:

–Yes [specify]: There were ceramics recovered from offerings at this temple so it is likely that these contained foods. Pumpkin and chile seeds were recovered from the excavations (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:147).

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– I don't know

Notes: Some animal remains were recovered from this context, however, it is not clear if these were sacrificed. The animals identified include dog or coyote, quail, wild turkey, aquatic bird (probably *Podylimbus podiceps*), frog, and unidentified fish remains (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:148).

↳ Human sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: infants and children encompass a large group of sacrifices (n = 30) to this deity but adults (n = 11; men and women) were also recovered from the temple's offerings (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:172)..

↳ Sacred objects:

– Yes [specify]: ceremonial ceramic vessels and male and female ceramic figurines; musical instruments, wood scepters with snake-like features, animal bone awl/piercing object (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:149-151, 155-165).

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: obsidian knives, domestic ceramics, copper beads and bracelets, shell pendants and beads, baskets, cotton clothing, wood (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:149-155, 166-172).

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: black, red, blue pigments on sculptures, ceramics, figurines, etc., resin (Guilliem Arroyo 1999:151,153-155).

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica priests and elite planned specific ceremonies during their established (20-day month) ritual calendar for their deities (including Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl) and during exceptional events such as times of famine and drought.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica would prepare for rituals and then would engage in specific performances as part of the ritual ceremony (including sacrifice in some instances). Specific clothing, objects, and food items were used for a range of ritual ceremonies, depending on the festivity and deity honored.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica tended to build ceremonial temples and later enlarge them in the same place. This speaks to the fact that they had to maintain the place and enlarge it as they began to have more resources, laborers, and overall power to do these expansions. Building expansions tended to coincide with the ascension of a new Mexica emperor (tlatoani).

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica were known for being extremely hygienic in their every day practices. Slaves chosen for a sacrificial ritual were bathed ahead of time as part of the cleansing and cleaning of these individuals so that the slave status would be washed away, but also they would end up being clean before being offered to the deities.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: The number is not known but we know that everyone from commoner to noble attended these rituals. The population of Tlatelolco would have been smaller than at Tenochtitlan (200,000) so somewhere under this number.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: during multiple monthly festivals throughout the ritual year as well as during one-time ceremonies.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The priests used intoxicants and some times intoxicants were given to sacrificial victims prior to the sacrificial act. I'm unsure if this was the case for particular rituals held at the Temple R, but these were used regularly enough that this could have been the case.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– I don't know

Notes: See note above on this. Animal remains were recovered but there is no information available to know if these were sacrificed.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– Yes

↳ Adults

– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Male

Notes: Males were identified based on the osteological analysis (Román Berrelleza 1991; Moreiras Reynaga et al. 2021).

↳ Children

– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

- Male
- Other/InD

Notes: Based on the chromosomal ancient DNA analysis carried out by De la Cruz et al. (2008), most of the subadults (ages 2 to 7) recovered from the Temple R were identified as male.

↳ Foreigners and/or slaves

- Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

- Male
- Other/InD

Notes: Based on the phosphate oxygen isotope analysis carried out by Moreiras Reynaga and colleagues (2021), we know that one adult male was a foreigner to the Basin of Mexico. The rest of the individuals analyzed had a Basin of Mexico oxygen isotope signal. They could have been born in the area or lived in the region for a long period before their sacrifice. It is possible that many of these individuals were purchased at the well-organized Mexica slave markets.

↳ Elites

- Field doesn't know

Notes: While we know that some times noble children were sacrificed at specific ritual ceremonies, it is uncertain if the individuals sacrificed at this temple would have belonged to the elite class. Since many of the children suffered multiple ailments and illnesses that were identified by Román Berrelleza (1991) in his paleopathological analysis, it is more likely that these children came from lower status households and/or slave markets.

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

- Yes [specify]: The majority were chosen for sacrifice between the ages of 2 and 7 years old and were male. Researchers have proposed that the subadults may have acted as tiny dwarf-like beings called "tlaloque", who were the rain god Tlaloc's little helpers (Román Berrelleza and Chávez Balderas 2006).

Are there self-sacrifices present:

- No

Are material offerings present:

- Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: In some instances. See note above about the objects that were recovered from the offerings.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Ceramic pottery, clothing, wood, etc. were also recovered from the offerings. See note above about all of the type of objects that were recovered from the offerings.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the material offerings were interred along with the human remains in specific ways and each offering was composed of a series of objects along with the human remains. The human remains were placed either on the ground or inside ceramic pots.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: The entire community attended the ceremonies in Mexica society.

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The Mexica elites and priests were in charge of arranging the ritual ceremonies so they had to attend and host the ceremonies.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

Notes: Not sure but it is likely that cleansing of the place could have been practiced.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica spent resources to make repairs as well as enlarge their temples in the same location.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: There were priests assigned to each temple so they would be the ones in charge of everything related to the maintenance of the place and of organizing everything for the ceremonies as well.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: There were specific months in the Mexica ritual calendar when they held ceremonies/festivals for the rain and wind deities prior to the arrival of the rains to bring a successful and fertile agricultural cycle.

Notes: There were a total of 18 festivals/ceremonies throughout their 18 months of 20 days each. These are known as "veintenas" in Spanish. There are multiple Mesoamerican codices that portray these festivals such as the Florentine Codex written by Fray Sahagún. There is a whole field of study in Mesoamerican history dedicated at studying and analyzing these pictographic texts to better understand the structure and details of these festivals.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– I don't know

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Notes: Sometimes feasting was involved after the ritual ceremonies and everyone participated in it and the elite provided the food for everyone.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– I don't know

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– I don't know

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While we don't know if they were present full time. We do know that priests were in charge of Mexica temples, so this could have been one in which a couple of priests were in charge of.

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Priests were male. They had specific education and training and specific physical characteristics such that they were recognizable amongst the rest of the population.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, they would have been Mexica.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: All priests belonged to a specific "priestly class" within the Mexica social structure. They enjoyed of respect and privilege just as the Mexica nobility, and they had many responsibilities related to the religious traditions of the Mexica society.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– I don't know

Notes: There are multiple codices (pictorial primary texts) that depicted Mexica temples. I'm not sure if this particular temple was depicted in these. Certainly the deity, Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl was depicted in the codices.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: There were priests in charge of specific temples, but I'm unsure of where within the ceremonial complex they would have lived.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While we don't know if they were present full time. We do know that priests were in charge of Mexica temples, so this could have been one in which a couple of priests were in charge of.

Present part time

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Priests were male. They had specific education and training and specific physical characteristics such that they were recognizable amongst the rest of the population.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

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Notes: Yes, they would have been Mexica.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

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Notes: All priests belonged to a specific "priestly class" within the Mexica social structure. They enjoyed of respect and privilege just as the Mexica nobility, and they had many responsibilities related to the religious traditions of the Mexica society.

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↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

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Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: There were priests in charge of specific temples, but I'm unsure of where within the ceremonial complex they would have lived.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– I don't know

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– I don't know

Notes: There are multiple codices (pictorial primary texts) that depicted Mexica temples. I'm not sure if this particular temple was depicted in these. Certainly the deity, Ehécatl-Quetzalcoatl was depicted in the codices.

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General References

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